

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 6

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 6

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна
*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi
*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович
*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Очилов Улугбек Усмонович
*PhD, доцент, СамДТУ Дипломдан кейинги таълим
факултети Психиатрия курси мудири. СамДТУ Илмий
кенгаши котиби. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Шавази Наргиз Нуралiena
*DSc. Доцент, СамДМУ 3-сон акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович
*Тоҷикистон Давлат тиббиёт университети Онкология
ва нур таъхиси кафедраси мудири, Тиббиёт фанлари
доктори, Профессор, Душанбе, Тоҷикистон.
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Сандов Сандамир Абборович
*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдуҷаббарович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович
*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович
*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталя Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаматовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Очилов Улугбек Усманович

PhD, доцент, заведующий курсом психиатрии
факультета постдипломного образования СамГМУ.
Секретарь Ученого совета СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>

Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc. доцент, заведующая кафедрой
акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Рашид Захидович

Заведующий кафедрой Онкологии и лучевой
диагностики Таджикского медицинского университета,
д.м.н., профессор, Душанбе, Таджикистан
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>

Саидов Сандамир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic ORCID ID: 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine, Tashkent
Medical Academy. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Ochilov Ulugbek Usmanovich

*PhD, Docent, Head of the Psychiatry Course at the Faculty of
Postgraduate Education of SamSMU. Secretary of the Academic
Council of SamSMU. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3553-8727>*

Shavazi Nargiz Nuraliyena

*DSc, Associate Professor, Head of the Department of Obstetrics
and Gynecology N 3 of Samarkand State Medical University.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>*

Yuldashev Ravshan Zakhidovich

*Head of the Department of Oncology and Radiation Diagnostics
at Tajik State Medical University, Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Professor. Dushanbe, Tajikistan <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7165-5373>*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxammatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Abdullaeva S. Lola, Kattakhodzhaeva K. Makhmuda**
RISK FACTORS AND DIAGNOSIS OF MASSIVE OBSTETRIC HEMORRHAGE.....9
2. **Agababyan R. Larisa, Isayeva CH. Sakhiba**
OPPORTUNITIES OF THE OPERATIVE LAPAROSCOPY IN GYNECOLOGICAL SURGERY.....15
3. **Muminjonova F. Iroda, Abdullayeva M. Lagiya**
USE OF RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH UTERINE MYOMA.....21
4. **Negmadjanov B. Bakhodur, Makhmudova E. Sevara**
GENETIC ASPECTS AND DIAGNOSIS OF CONGENITAL MALFORMATIONS OF THE GENITALS.....26
5. **Zufarova A. Shaxnoza., Eshdavlatov E. Ilkhom**
PATHOGENETIC MECHANISMS OF "EPITHELIAL-MESENCHYMAL TRANSITIONS" IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADHESIVE DISEASE DURING SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN GYNECOLOGY.....34

EXPERIMENTAL BIOMEDICINE

6. **Allahverdiyev E. Emin, Alekberova K. Chimnaz, Nasibova R. Gunel, Mammadova K. Tacli, Jafarova R. Aygun, Huseynov R. Kanan**
TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF POSTPARTUM PARESIS.....40
7. **Verdiyeva E. Leyla, Nasibova R. Gunel, Mammadova A. Ayten, Abbasov H. Seymur, Quluyeva M. Aida**
RECOVERY OVARIAN ACTIVITY AFTER CALVING.....44
8. **Rasulov Kh. Alisher, Ibragimov S. Abdurahmon, Makhmudov D. Sardor, Turaev S. Abbasxon, Shadmanov K. Kamoliddin**
GOSSYPOL IS A SUBSTANCE WITH UNIQUE PROPERTIES: FEATURES AND PROSPECTS FOR APPLICATION IN VARIOUS FIELDS OF SCIENCE AND PRODUCTION.....48
9. **Hikmatulaev Z. Rukhulla**
IMMUNOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF SPINAL CORD INJURY BIOMARKER S100B IN EXPERIMENTAL ANIMAL MODEL.....57

INFECTION AND INFECTIOUS DISEASES

10. **Abduvakhitova N. Indira**
EVALUATION OF HUMORAL IMMUNITY INDICATORS IN HERPES-ASSOCIATED ERYTHEMA MULTIFORME.....63
11. **Sayfutdinov A. Zainiddin**
MICROBIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF WIDESPREAD DRUG-RESISTANT PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS.....68

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

12. **Karabayeva X. Zilola, Nasretdinova T. Maxzuna**
EPIDEMIOLOGY OF CHRONIC OCCUPATIONAL ALLERGIC RHINITIS IN FIBERGLASS WORKERS FIBERGLASS INDUSTRY.....73
13. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher**
MAXILLARY SINUS CYSTS, CLINIC, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT.....78

14. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
ANALYSIS OF MICROBIAL FLORA IN PATIENTS WITH COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHRONIC PURULENT OTITIS MEDIA.....84
15. **Safoeva F. Zebo, Usmanova B. Kamila, Bakiev Sh. Shavkatbek**
THE EFFECT OF GENE POLYMORPHISM ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF LARYNGOTRACHEITIS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....92
16. **Samyeva U. Gulnoza, Sabirova B. Shakhlo, Bakhranova Sh. Malika**
IMPROVEMENT OF DIAGNOSTICS AND OPTIMIZATION OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LARYNGITIS.....99

RADIATION DIAGNOSTICS

17. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira** FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT OF PATIENTS WITH NODULAR FORMATIONS OF THE THYROID GLAND.....105
18. **Gaybullaev O. Sherzod, Khamidov A. Obid**
THE ROLE OF RADIOLOGY IN REHABILITATION CENTERS: MODERN PROSPECTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....111
19. **Khamidov A. Obid.**
TELEMEDICINE IN REHABILITATION CENTERS: IMPROVING DIAGNOSTIC QUALITY THROUGH TELE-DIAGNOSIS.....118

MORFOLOGY

20. **Boymanov Kh. Farxod, Shukurova U. Yulduz, Allaberganov Sh. Dilshod**
MICROSCOPIC CHANGES IN INFANT LUNG TISSUE MORTALITY IN ANTENATAL PERIOD125
21. **Gaipov A. Dilmurod, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN THE FACET JOINTS OF THE LUMBAR SPINE.....132
22. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira**
HISTO-PATHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES ACCORDING TO THE BETHESDA CLASSIFICATION.....141
23. **Achilova U. Ozoda, Kayumov A. Abdurakhman, Mahamadalieva Z. Gulchehra**
MORPHOLOGICAL PICTURE OF BONE MARROW IN PATIENTS IN THE EARLY PERIOD AFTER ALLOGENEIC HEMATOPOIETIC CELL TRANSPLANTATION.....147

NEUROLOGY AND PSYCHIATRY

24. **Rasulova K. Dilbar**
THE ROLE OF CLINICAL AND LABORATORY PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS IN THE ACUTE PERIOD OF STROKE TO PREDICT REHABILITATION POTENTIAL.....155
25. **Muxidova X. Gulmira, Teshayev J. Mashrab**
COMPUTER ADDICTION IN TEENAGERS.....161
26. **Saidvaliyev S. Farrukh, Subkhanova Kh. Aziza**
ROLE OF ANTIDEPRESSANTS IN REDUCING THE FREQUENCY AND DURATION OF MIGRAINE HEADACHES.....165

PUBLIC HEALTH

27. **Kamishov V. Sergey, Balenkov Y. Oleg, Niyazov G. Akmal**
ANALYSIS OF TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF COMPULSORY HEALTH INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN.....170

ONCOLOGY

28. **Khodjamova A. Gulbakhor, Zulfkorov Z. Khasan, Nigmadjonov S. Abdurashid**
ULTRASONOGRAPHY IN PREDICTING BENIGN OR MALIGNANT NATURE OF SOFT TISSUE FORMATIONS.....178
29. **Mamarizaev D. Yu.**
FEATURES OF MANAGEMENT AND SURGICAL TREATMENT OF MALIGNANT PHEOCHROMOCYTOMA.....186
30. **Khamrakulova N.O., Kazimov B.B.**
MODERN VIEW ON THE PROBLEM OF DIAGNOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH ANGIOFIBROMA OF THE NASOPHARYNX BY DETECTING POLYMORPHISM OF THE GSTM1 GENE199
31. **Dadakhanova B. Maryamkhon, KHalimova Yu. Zamira**
EFFECTIVENESS OF APPLYING THE ACR TI-RADS CLASSIFICATION IN PATIENTS WITH THYROID NODULES FOR FINE-NEEDLE ASPIRATION BIOPSY.....210

THERAPY

32. **Tuychieva K.Sabokhat, Tashkenbaeva N.Eleonora**
PPARG: GENETIC MARKER FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE AND METABOLIC DISORDERS.....217

TRAUMATOLOGY

33. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Temurov A. Alisher, Nurumov Yo. Sarvat, Ziyotov I.Laziz**
RESULTS OF ENDOPROSTHETICS IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH HIP FRACTURES.....227
34. **Akramov R. Vohid**
METHOD FOR PREVENTION OF EARLY DISLOCATIONS OF ENDOPROTHESIS IN PATIENTS WITH II-III DEGREE DYSPLASTIC COXARTHROSIS.....234
35. **Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek, Fattakhov A. Ravshan**
ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH UNILATERAL ANTERIOR DISCLOSATION OF THE TMJ ARTICULAR DISC.....238

SURGERY

36. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor**
MODERN ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VENTRAL HERNIA WITH CONCOMITANT ABDOMINOPTOSIS245
37. **Rakhmanov E. Kosim, Khamdamov D. Olim**
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF PULMONARY ECHINOCOCCOSIS.256
38. **Khamdamov D. Olim, Rakhmanov E. Kosim**
MODERN APPROACHES TO SURGICAL TREATMENT OF THORACIC ECHINOCOCCOSIS: EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND RADICAL METHODS.....263
39. **Sattarov Kh. Shokir**
CURRENT APPROACHES TO TREATMENT THE PATIENTS WITH WIDESPREAD PURULENT PERITONITIS.....268
40. **Xujabaev T. Safarboy, Dusiyarov M. Mukhammad**
PREDICTION OF COMPLICATIONS OF HERNIOPLASTY (Literature review).....276
41. **Zayniyev F. Alisher, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
OPTIMIZATION OF METHODS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF TOXIC GOITER.....282

42. **Shonazarov Sh. Iskandar, Karimov S. Sardor**
OPTIMISATION OF TACTICAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE AND RECURRENT VENTRAL HERNIAS.....288
43. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Sulaymanov U. Salim, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
EVALUATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMPLICATIONS OF CHOLELITHIASIS.....296
44. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Baratov B. Manon, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
STAGE SURGICAL TACTICS FOR TREATING COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHOLELITHIASIS IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS: EFFECTIVENESS AND RESULTS302
45. **Arziyev A. Ismoil, Nazarov N. Zokir, Arziyeva B. Gulnora**
CLINICAL ANALYSIS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BILE DUCT INJURIES DURING OPERATIONS.....312
46. **Kadirov N. Rustam, Abdikadirov A. Ulugbek, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
THERAPEUTIC APPLICATIONS OF MINIMALLY INVASIVE DECOMPRESSION PROCEDURES IN THE SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF CHOLANGITIS.....321
47. **Abdikadirov A. Ulugbek, Kadirov N. Rustam, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar Bobojonovich**
THERAPEUTIC APPLICATION OF PLASMAPHERESIS IN SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF ACUTE BENIGN CHOLANGITIS.....330

CHILDREN SURGERY

48. **Chuliev S. Matyoqub**
PURULENT ARTHRITIS IN CHILDREN, CAUSES, CLINIC, DIAGNOSIS, PRINCIPLES OF TREATMENT.....339

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

49. **Khotamova A. Madina, Nazarova Sh. Nodira, Bahridinova R. Mohidil**
CLINICAL MEASURES AND OCCUPATIONAL HYGIENE IN THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL DISEASES AND DISCUSSION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PREVENTIVE MEASURES344
50. **Kubayev S. Aziz, Anvarova A. Muxtasar**
ASSESSMENT OF CHEWING EFFICIENCY AND INDICATORS OF ORAL DRY METABOLISM IN CHILDREN WITH ANOMALIES OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL SYSTEM353
51. **Sadriyev N. Nizom, Musayeva A. Gulchekhra**
CLINICAL AND LABORATORY ASSESSMENT OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES OF VIRAL ETIOLOGY.....357
52. **Abdurashidov A. Oybekjon**
MODERN PROBLEMS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ORAL CANDIDIASIS.....366
53. **Islamova B. Nilufar**
ORTHOPEDIC CASES OF ERRORS IN PROSTHETICS ON IMPLANTS.....371
54. **Anvarova A. Muxtasar**
TO EVALUATE THE ORAL MASTICATORY ABILITY AND METABOLIC PARAMETERS OF PATIENTS UNDERGOING UROPLASTY.....376
55. **Tulaganov A. Nozim**
ANALYSIS OF MAXILLARY SINUS CONDITION IN TRAUMATIC INJURIES OF THE ZYGOMATIC-ORBITAL REGION.....380

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

56. **Indiaminov I. Sayit, Kurmasheva K. Jamila.**
FORENSIC ASPECTS OF SEXUAL ABUSE OF GIRLS AND TEENAGE GIRLS.....391

БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ БИОМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ | JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

U.O.K:004.94:616.857-036-08

SAIDVALIYEV Farrukh Saidakramovich
SUBKHANOVA Aziza Khabibulla kizi

Tashkent medical academy

ROLE OF ANTIDEPRESSANTS IN REDUCING THE FREQUENCY AND DURATION OF MIGRAIN HEADACHES

For citation: Saidvaliyev S. Farrukh, Subkhanova Kh. Aziza. Role of antidepressants in reducing the frequency and duration of migraine headaches// Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 6, pp.165-169

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14605465>

ANNOTATION

Migraine headache is a chronic neurological disease and is the fourth most commonly diagnosed disease in the world. In many cases, patient diagnosed with migraine also develop depression, which hinders treatment and leads to overuse of medication. In a scientific study, the effectiveness of antidepressant medication in the treatment of migraine in addition to the main standard medical treatment was studied in order to reduce the number, duration and level of depression in patients diagnosed with migraine.

Keywords: migraine, depression, pharmacological treatment, behavioral therapy, preventive treatment.

SAIDVALIYEV Farruh Saidakramovich
SUBKHANOVA Aziza Xabibulla qizi

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi

MIGREN BOSH OG‘RIQ SONINI VA DAVOMIYLIGINI KAMAYTIRISHDA ANTIDEPRESSANT DORI VOSITASINING O‘RNI

ANNOTATSIYA

Migren- bosh og‘rig‘i surunkali nevrologik kasallik bo‘lib, dunyo bo‘yicha ko‘p tashxislanadigan kasalliklar orasida to‘rtinchi o‘rinda turadi. Ko‘p hollarda migren tashxisi qo‘yilgan bemorlarda depressiya ham rivojlanadi, bu esa davolanishga to‘sqinlik qiladi va dori-darmonlarni haddan tashqari ko‘p suiiste‘mol qilishga olib keladi. Ilmiy ishda migren tashxisi qo‘yilgan bemorlarda bosh og‘riq sonini, davomiyligini va depressiya darajasini kamaytirish maqsadida asosiy standart davo muolajasiga qo‘shimcha ravishda antidepressant dori vositasini migrenni davolashda samarasini o‘rganilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: migren, depressiya, farmakologik davo, xulq-atvor terapiyasi, profilaktik davo.

САИДВАЛИЕВ Фаррух Саидакрамович
СУБХАНОВА Азиза Хабибулла кизи

Ташкентская медицинская академия

РОЛЬ АНТИДЕПРЕССАНТОВ В СНИЖЕНИИ ЧАСТОТЫ И ПРОДОЛЖИТЕЛЬНОСТИ МИГРЕНОЗНЫХ ГОЛОВНЫХ БОЛЕЙ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мигрень — это хроническое неврологическое заболевание, которое занимает четвертое место среди самых распространенных заболеваний во всем мире. В большинстве случаев у пациентов с диагнозом мигрень развивается депрессия, что препятствует лечению и приводит к чрезмерному злоупотреблению лекарствами. В целях снижения количества, продолжительности головных болей и степени депрессии у пациентов с диагнозом «мигрень» в научной работе изучается эффективность антидепрессантов в лечении мигрени в дополнение к основному стандарту лечения.

Ключевые слова: мигрень, депрессия, фармакологическое лечение, поведенческая терапия, профилактическое лечение.

Kirish. Migren - bosh og'rig'i birlamchi nevrologik kasallik bo'lib, 4 soatdan 72 soatgacha davom etadi. Odatda og'riq bir tomonlama yoki ikki tomonlama, pulsatsiyalanuvchi, o'rtacha va kuchli darajadagi bosh og'rig'i, jismoniy faollikda kuchayishi, ko'ngil aynishi, qayd qilish, fonofobiya yoki fotofobiya bilan kuzatiladi. Migrenda aura belgilari bosh og'rig'idan oldin paydo bo'lishi mumkin [1]. Migren rivojlanishida gormonlar faoliyati, genetik omillar, atrof-muhit, oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari va psixologik omillar, shuningdek, uyqu rejimini buzilishi alohida ahamiyatga ega [2]. Migren va bosh og'rig'i ko'pincha hissiy muammolar bilan bog'liq. Migren xastaligida depressiyaning birga kelishi ko'p hollarda aniqlangan. Haqiqatan ham, migrenning surunkali turida bosh og'rig'ining epizodik turiga nisbatan depressiya holatlari ko'p uchraydi [3]. Migren bosh og'rig'in oldini olish uchun antidepressantlardan foydalanish dastlab umumiy ta'sir mexanizmlari haqidagi tasodifiy kashfiyotlar va taxminlarga asoslangan edi. Antidepressantlarning depressiyani davolashda solishtirma samaradorligi aniqlangab bo'lib, ushbu guruh dori vositalarini tanlash ko'pincha yondosh kasalliklar, simptomatologiya shakllari, oldingi davolash javobi va bir vaqtning o'zida qabul qilingan dorilar bilan belgilanadi. Biroq, ularning surunkali og'riqlar va bosh og'rig'i kasalliklari uchun samaradorligi sezilarli darajada farq qiladi [4]. Migren bosh og'rig'i kasalliklarini boshqarishda qo'shimcha klinik samaradorlikka erishish uchun xulq-atvor ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish va farmakologik davo muolajalari bilan birlashtirilishi mumkinligi keng tarqalgan [5]. Surunkali migren bilan og'rikan bemorlar bosh og'rig'i bo'lmagan odamlarga qaraganda ikki yoki besh baravar ko'proq depressiya holatlari qayd etiladi [6]. Migren bosh og'rig'i aniqlangan bemorlarni davolash bo'yicha xalqaro tavsiyalar hali ishlab chiqilmagan. Standart davo usullari (profilaktik farmakoterapiya, umumiy quvvatlovchi va xulq-atvor ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish) bo'yicha ma'lumotlar bazasi yetarlicha o'rganilmagan [7]. Xulq-atvor terapiyasi bemorning o'z kasalligi bo'yicha bilim darajasini oshirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Uyqusizlik va gipersomniya migren hujumining qo'zg'atuvchi omillari va migrenning surunkali omillari hisoblanadi. Barcha bemorlarga uyqu sifatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadigan barcha omillarni bartaraf etish tavsiya etiladi (uyqu rejimiga amal qilish, kofeinni ortiqcha iste'mol qilish, spirtli ichimliklar, ovqatlanish rejimiga rioya qilish, o'rtacha jismoniy faollik va boshqalar) [8].

Tadqiqot maqsadi: antidepressant dori vositasining migren bosh og'rig'iga samarasini baholash.

Tadqiqot usullari va materiallari: tadqiqotga Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi maslaxat poliklinikasi va "Alisher Shifo Med Tashmi" xususiy klinikasida ambulator sharoitda murojaat qilgan 18 yoshdan 55 yoshgacha migren tashxisi qo'yilgan 200 nafar bemorlar jalb qilindi. Ulardan ayollar 163 nafar, erkaklar 37 nafarni tashkil etdi. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra bemorlarning jins bo'yicha taqqoslanganda erkaklarga qaraganda ayollar ko'prog'ini tashkil qildi. Ayollar va erkaklar 4:1 nisbatni uchradi. Barcha bemorlarda anamnez, instrumentral, klinik-nevrologik tekshiruvlar so'rovnomasida o'tkazildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari: Tekshiruvga jalb qilinganlar orasida 200 nafar migren tashxisi qo'yilgan bemorlar tanlab olindi va ularda xulq-atvor ko'nikma va xastalikga oid bilimlarni

shakllantirish hamda depressiyani kamaytirish maqsadida uch guruhga bo'ldik. Shulardan I guruh (n=60 nafar, migrenning standart farmokologik davosi va og'zaki nazorat kundaligi) bemorlarning 48 nafar (30%) ayollar, 12 nafari (32%) erkaklar, II guruh (n=68 nafar, migren standart davosi va qog'oz shaklidagi nazorat kundaligi) bemorlarning 56 nafar (34%) ayol, 11 nafar (30%) erkak, III guruh (n=72 nafar, migren standart davosi va «MIGREN PRO» mobil ilovasi) bemorning 59 nafar (36%) ayol, 14 nafar (38%) erkak kishidan iborat bo'ldi (1-jadval).

1-jadval.

Tadqiqot birinchi bosqich sub'yektlarining jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha taqsimlanishi.

Jinsi	I guruh n=60	II guruh n=68	III guruh n=72
Ayol n(%)	48 (30%)	56 (34%)	59 (36%)
Erkak n(%)	12 (32%)	11 (30%)	14 (38%)
O'rtacha yosh	38,3±7,4	35,2±4,8	33,3±4,1

Izoh: *ishonchlilik ko'rsatgichi, p<0,05.

Migrenning epizodik va surunkali kechishi bo'yicha taxlillar so'rovnoma asosida o'tkazildi. Jami 200 nafar bemordan 173 nafarida (86%) epizodik migren, qolgan 27 nafarida (14%) statistik ahamiyatga ega kam darajada surunkali migren aniqlandi (p<0,05). Migrenning aurali va aurasiz kechishi bo'yicha o'rganilganda epizodik migren aniqlangan bemorlarning 41 nafar (23%) aurali migren, 132 nafar (77%) aurasiz migren aniqlandi. Surunkali migren aniqlangan bemorlarda 8 nafar (30%) aurali, 19 nafar (70%) aurasiz migren kuzatildi. Olingan natijalarda migrenning aurali va aurasiz kechishi bo'yicha tahlil natijalariga ko'ra umumiy migren tashxisi qo'yilgan bemorlar orasida statistik ahamiyatga ega ravishda aurasiz migren ko'p uchradi (p<0,05). Asosiy uchta guruhdagi bemorlarda epizodik va surunkali migren aniqlandi, ularning har ikki turida ham migrenning aurali va aurasiz kechishi aniqlanib, aurali kechishining bir qancha turlari qayd etildi va olingan natijalar quyidagicha baholandi; oftalmik aura epizodik migren aniqlangan I guruhda 6 nafar (60%) , II guruhda 10 nafar (71%), III guruhda 6 nafar (75%) bemorda aniqlandi. Retinal aura I guruhda 4 nafar (40%), II guruhda 4 nafar (29%), III guruhda 2 nafar (25%) bemorda uchradi, qolgan aura turlari aniqlanmadi.

1-rasm. Aurali migren turlarini guruhlarda uchrash tahlili.

Surunkali migrenda retinal aura I guruhda aniqlanmadi 0%, II guruhda 2 nafar (67%), III guruhda 2 nafar (50%) bemorda kuzatildi. Bazilyar aura I guruhda 1 nafar (100%), II guruhda ham 1 nafar (33%), III guruhda 2 nafar (50%) bemorda kuzatildi, boshqa aura turlari aniqlanmadi (1-rasm). Oftalmik aura epizodik migrenda aniqlanib, surunkali migrenda kuzatilmadi, retinal va bazilyar aura surunkali migrenda epizodik migrenga qaraganda ko'proq aniqlandi, guruhlar o'rtasida aura turi uchrashi bo'yicha statistik ahamiyatli farq aniqlandi p<0,05.

Migrenning epizodik va surunkali turida bosh og'riq darajasi, depressiya, kundalik ish faoliyati va hayot sifatini taqqoslama natijalari o'rganildi.

2-rasm. Epizodik migren aniqlangan bemorlarda klinik kechishini baholash.

Olingan natijalarga ko‘ra epizodik migren aniqlangan bemorlarda VASH shkalasi o‘rtacha $7,8 \pm 0,6$ ball, surunkali migrenda $10,0 \pm 1,9$ ball. Depressiya darajasi epizodik migrenda o‘rtacha $14,6 \pm 2,4$ ball, surunkali migrenda $18,9 \pm 3,7$ ball. MIDAS shkalasida esa epizodik migren $19,3 \pm 2,2$ ball, surunkali migren $21,5 \pm 2,8$ ball aniqlandi. QVM so‘rovnomasida epizodik migren $44,3 \pm 4,1$ ball, surunkali migrenda $41,7 \pm 3,6$ ballni tashkil etdi ($p < 0,05$) 2 va 3 rasm.

3-rasm. Surunkali migren aniqlangan bemorlarda klinik kechishini baholash.

Bemorlarda neyrovizual tekshiruv xulosasi natijalariga ko‘ra turli darajadagi bosh miyada turli o‘zgarishlari aniqlandi va Fazekas shkalasi yordamida baholandi. Epizodik migren bilan I guruhda 74%, II guruhda 80%, III guruhda esa 96% Fazekas 0 darajasi aniqlandi. Fazeks 1 bilan esa I guruh 26%, II guruh 20%, III guruh 4% uchradi. Surunkali migren bilan esa Fazeks 0 I guruhda uchramadi (0%), II guruhda 67%, III guruhda 20% aniqlandi. Fazeks 1 I guruhda 3 nafar (100%), II guruhda 33%, III guruhda 80% kuzatildi. Tadqiqotimizda epizodik migren ko‘p uchraganligi bilan Fazekas 0 da bemorlar soni ko‘p uchradi va guruhlar o‘rtasida statistik ahamiyatga ega farq aniqlandi $p < 0,05$. Xulosa qilib aytganda, migrenning epizodik turida Fazeks 0 turi bo‘yicha bosh miyada o‘zgarishlar aniqlanmadi. Fazeks 1 turi esa epizodik va surunkali migrenda uchradi. O‘z navbatida epizodik migrenda Fazekas shkalasi bo‘yicha past darajada bo‘lishi kuzatildi.

Tadqiqotimiz davomida biz bemorlarda bosh og‘riqlar soni, davomiyligi va depressiya darajasini kamaytirish maqsadida asosiy standart davo muolajasiga qo‘shimcha ravishda antidepressant guruhiga mansub Essitalopram dori vositasining migrenni davolashdagi samarasini o‘rgandik. Essitalopram dori vositasining samarasini o‘rganishda biz tadqiqotga jalb qilingan guruhlar ichidan xulq-atvoriga oid ko‘nikma va bilimlarni shakllantirishda va davo samaradorligini baholashda yuqori natijaga ega «MIGREN PRO» mobil ilovasidan foydalangan III guruh ($n=72$) bemorlarini tanlab olib, ularni 2 kichik guruhga bo‘ldik. I kichik guruhdagi 36 nafar bemorga migrenning standart davo muolajasiga qo‘shimcha ravishda Essitalopram dori vositasi 10 mg 1 ta tabletka 1 mahal ertalab ovqatlanishdan so‘ng 2 oy muddatda qabul qilish tavsiya etildi, II kichik guruhdagi 36 nafar bemorga esa faqat migrenning standart davosi buyurildi. Bemorlar nazoratga olindi va dinamikada kuzatuvda bo‘ldi. 3 oydan so‘ng davo muolajalarining samaradorligi baholandi, unga ko‘ra: o‘rtacha bosh og‘riq miqdori I gr $2,9 \pm 1,7$ ball, II guruhda $5,3 \pm 1,4$ ball. Bosh og‘riq

darajasi I guruhda $3,5 \pm 0,3$, II guruhda $5,2 \pm 0,6$. Bosh og'riq davomiyligi I guruhda $22,7 \pm 0$ min, II guruhda $40,9 \pm 9,8$ min. Depressiya darajasi $6,4 \pm 1,5$ ball, II guruhda $8,6 \pm 2,1$ ball tashkil etdi. Essitalopram dori vositasini qabul qilgan I guruh bemorlarida bosh og'riqlari soni, darajasi, davomiyligi va depressiya darajasi statistik jihatdan ahamiyatli darajada kamaydi, $p < 0,05$.

Xulosa: tadqiqotimiz davomida xulq-atvorga oid ko'nikma va bilimlarni shakllantirishda «MIGREN PRO» mobil ilovasidan foydalanib, yuqori darajadagi davolash samaradorligiga erishgan III guruh bemorlarida Essitalopram dori vositasining migren bosh og'rig'i va depressiya darajasiga ta'siri o'rganildi va bu bemorlar ikkita guruhga ajratilib, davolashning samaradorligi baholandi. Natijalarga ko'ra, standart davo muolajasiga qo'shimcha ravishda Essitalopram dori vositasini qabul qilgan bemorlarda (I guruh) Essitalopram dori vositasini qabul qilmagan (II guruh) bemorlarga qaraganda bosh og'riqlar soni, davomiyligi va depressiya darajasi sezilarli darajada kamayganligi qayd etildi.

REFERENCES | ЧОККИ | ИҚТИБОСЛАР:

1. The International Classification of Headache Disorder, 3rd edition (beta version) Headache Classification Committee of the International Headache Society (IHS) Cephalgiya. 2013;33;629-808. Doi: 10.1177/0333102413485658/
2. Anxiety and depression symptoms and migraine: a symptom-based approach research. Peres MF, Mercante JP, Tobo PR, Kamei H, Bigal ME Pain. 2017;18;37. Doi: 10.1186/s10194-017-0742-1.
3. Cacciatore M, raggi A, Cristilo V, Pilotto A, Guastafierro E, Toppo C, Magnani FG, sattin D, Cotti Piccinelli S, Gipponi S, Librii I, Bezzi M, Martelletti P, Leonardi M, padovani A (2022) Neurological and Mental Health Symptoms associated with Post- COVID-19 Disability in a Sample of Patients discharged from a COVID-19 Ward: A secondary Analysis. Int J environ Res Public Health 19:4242.
4. Stonver LJ, Tronvic E, hagen K. New drugs for migraine. J Headache Pain 2009; 10:395-406.
5. Holroyd KA, Penzion DB, Rains JC, Lipchik GL, Buse DC. Behavioral management of headache In: Silberstein SD, Lipton RB, Dodick DW, editors. Wolff's headacha and other head pain, 8th ed New York: Oxford University Press, 2008;721-746.
6. Silberstein SD. Preventive migraine treatment. Continuum. 2015;21:973-89 A comprehensive and authoritative review of the approach to preventive strategies for migraine.
7. Фитатова ЕГ, Осипова ВВ, Табаева ГР и др. Диагностика и лечение мигрени: рекомендации российских экспертов. Неврология, нейропсихиатрия, психосоматика. 2020;12(4):4-14. Doi: 10,14412/2074-2711-2020-4-4-14.
8. Harris P., Loveman E., Clegg A. at.al. Sustematic review of cognitive behavioral therapy for the managment of headaches and migraines in adults // Br.J.Pain.2015.Vol.9(4).P.213-224.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 6 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 6

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 6

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000